

WAYS TO INCREASE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract Today, the experience of many developed and leading countries shows that to achieve competitiveness and enter the world markets, first of all, consistent reform of the economy, structural change and deepening of diversification, ensuring the development of new enterprises and production industries based on high technologies, modernization of operating capacities and acceleration of technical update processes is required.

Keywords: Economic efficiency, working capital, economic activity, labor productivity, technological processes.

Ways to increase the economic efficiency of the enterprise include the introduction of scientific and technological progress, including the revolutionary re-equipment of production funds based on the latest scientific achievements of technology and technologies. Involvement of technical, organizational, social and economic factors, involvement of technical, organizational, social and economic factors significantly increases labor productivity.

Increasing the efficiency of the economic efficiency of the enterprise is a constant task of the enterprise's management. Solving this task in practice depends on the following factors:

- choosing the optimal production process that provides the maximum volume of production with the lowest costs in the production of high-quality products that meet market requirements;

- selling products aimed at satisfying consumer demand and obtaining high income (profit);

- creation of optimal production reserves, which makes it possible to save working capital.

In 2023, the production volume of industrial products increased by 5.6 percent compared to the corresponding period of 2022.

Today, almost 70 thousand industrial enterprises are operating in Uzbekistan, of which 11.5 thousand belong to the city of Tashkent, 7.9 thousand to the Fergana region, 7.1 thousand to the Tashkent region, and 6.2 thousand to the Samarkand region. .

In 2023, the volume of industrial production by types of economic activity:

- textile products - 33.3 trillion soums;

- clothing production - 10 trillion soums;-metallurgiya sanoati – 57,8 trln so‘m;

- chemical products - 16 trillion soums.

In 2022, the total number of operating enterprises and organizations (excluding farms and peasant farms) will be 554,971, an increase of 46,465 compared to the same period last year, and the growth rate will be 109.1 percent.

The number of operating enterprises and organizations by year:

Growth trends of production enterprises in Uzbekistan over the years ¹

№	years	the number
1.	2017- year	285 686
2.	2018- year	303 343
3.	2019- year	366 181
4.	2020- year	426 186
5.	2021- year	508 506
6.	2022- year	554 971

¹ Stat.uz information

Each of the above-mentioned factors of increasing economic efficiency is implemented with the help of various forms and forms of activity, taking into account the interaction of costs and resources underlying production efficiency. Evaluation of economic efficiency can be carried out according to the types of resources used in the enterprise and measured in terms of quantity. For example, the efficiency of the use of labor force can be evaluated with the help of indicators of labor productivity and labor capacity of the product. The labor capacity of the product is the inverse of labor productivity, and is defined as the ratio of the amount of labor spent to the volume of the produced product. The efficiency of the use of labor tools (fixed funds) is determined using the fund capacity and fund return indicators of the product. In this case, the fund return means the produced product corresponding to one unit of the main funds of the enterprise, and the fund capacity is the inverse of the fund return, and it performs the task of determining the capital investments necessary for the establishment of new main funds. The higher the fund return and the lower the fund capacity, the higher the efficiency of the use of production and labor tools, and vice versa. Efficient use of machines and equipment, improvement of production technologies and improvement of staff qualifications are important resources for increasing fund return. The efficiency of the use of labor tools is determined by the ratio of the total cost of raw materials, materials, fuel, energy and labor items consumed using the material capacity of the products to the volume of the produced product. The lower the material capacity of the product, the higher the production efficiency. However, the product should not be made at the expense of reducing the capacity of the material, reducing its quality, or violating the norms and rules of technology. Reducing material capacity in this way is considered an economic crime and is punishable by law. In market conditions, profitability or return on capital can be accepted as a general or standard indicator of the efficiency of the enterprise's economic activity. An

increase in the ratio means a more effective use of labor, finance, technology and material resources. Because it is they who affect the volume and costs of production, the price of the product. Economic activity is more effective in places where high-quality products are produced with minimal costs.

Increasing the economic efficiency of enterprise activity, the market system of economic management is an important requirement of any era. Efficiency reflects the economic stability and ability to operate any enterprise. The absence of efficiency and positive results in any work, including the activities of enterprises, can be explained figuratively speaking as a waste of time, energy and resources. Scientific and technical progress has been an important factor in increasing the efficiency of production activities of enterprises and has not lost its importance even now. This factor can be used in the following ways:

- *mechanization, automation and complex mechanization of production and labor;*
- *robotization of the main technological processes;*
- *implementation and wide use of progressive, labor and resource-saving technological processes;*
- *creation and use of modern types of raw materials and materials (objects of work);*
- *use of modern information technologies, computing techniques in production organization, planning and management processes;*
- *scientific organization of production and work.*

In practice, it is almost impossible to find an enterprise that denies or does not understand the importance and role of scientific and technical progress, including its components. However, only desires and wishes are not enough to implement this factor. For this, firstly, to search and identify the currently necessary directions of scientific and technical development, secondly, to find funds and other necessary resources (investments), and thirdly, scientific research

specialized in modern scientific and technical developments. institutes, construction, technological and other scientific institutions to "connect" the necessary connections, fourthly, it is required to calculate the effectiveness of its scientific and technical goals. The development of science and technology has been evolving until recently. The main focus was on the improvement of existing technologies, partial modernization of machines and equipment. Such measures would lead to certain limited results. Interest in the development and implementation of new techniques was not at the level of demand. Foreign progressive technologies of production and labor organization were perceived as "a sign of exploitation", and automation and mechanization of production were perceived as the basis of unemployment. Foreign experiences were considered capitalistic and were not allowed to spread widely.

In the current conditions in which market relations are being formed, it is necessary to undergo deep quality changes, transition to the principles of new technologies and the latest generation techniques, and to rearm all sectors of the economy based on the latest achievements of science and technology. At the same time, it is important to create economic and social interests for scientists, designers, engineers and workers to work in a creative spirit. For example, creative groups and quality groups have been established in Japanese enterprises and firms, that is, relations are being developed with universities, scientific centers and laboratories that are inextricably linked with the development of science and technology. It is no coincidence that today Japan ranks first in the creation of robots and other types of modern techniques and technologies.

As one of the important factors of increasing the efficiency of the production activity of enterprises, it is possible to show the most effective use of the existing production potential - fixed and circulating funds, labor force as efficiently as possible. In addition, it can be explained by the fact that they have spent commoditized labor, that is, the labor of representatives of the previous generation,

in addition to the current owners of the enterprise. The need for effective use of production potential in market conditions is seen in the following:

-firstly, the market does not forgive inactivity, lack of economy and losses,
-secondly, an enterprise that does not use its capabilities and resources sufficiently will not have prospects and will create a basis for bankruptcy. Therefore, the effective use of all types of resources and especially the observance of economy at all stages of production is the guarantee of the success of every enterprise. Organizational and economic factors, including management, play an important role in increasing the efficiency of production activities of enterprises. Their importance increases with the growth of the scale of production and the complexity of economic relations. Among these factors, in the first place, it is possible to include the creation of rational forms of production and the improvement of existing ones - concentration, specialization, cooperation and combination. And in management, it is expressed in the improvement of the methods and forms of management, planning, economic stimulation, that is, the entire economic mechanism of enterprise activity. The work style and methods of the head of the enterprise must be compatible with the development of science and technology and the market economy. For example, the director of the enterprise should be higher than ordinary employees and heads of departments (services) according to his knowledge, experience and professional qualifications. Otherwise, it is difficult for him to manage the team in the right way and to achieve success and have an image. Balancing of plans, optimal formation of the system of indicators, provision of planned goals with resources is of great importance in planning. This, in turn, requires the strengthening of economic activity in the enterprise, the selection of literate and qualified economists who are familiar with planning and economic calculations, as well as modern computer technology and its capabilities in the implementation of planned economic calculations.

Factors such as intensifying production, increasing the type and quality of manufactured products and bringing them up to world standards, and improving the production structure of the enterprise play an important role in the effectiveness of the enterprise. This is achieved through the use of modern machines and equipment, modern technologies, advanced methods of production and labor organization. Of course, the implementation of the above-mentioned factors requires spending certain resources and time. However, this does not change the nature and importance of the problems. Practice shows that an enterprise that keeps pace with the times, adheres to economy in all types of activities, uses its potential more effectively, relies on modern science and technology achievements, will achieve success in the future in addition to its success today, including in the market. ensures that it is in a favorable position in the competitive environment. Ways to increase the efficiency of the enterprise means using the economy mode. Resource conservation factors must be decisive to meet the continuous need for fuel, raw materials, materials and energy. In addition, ways to increase the efficiency of the enterprise include activities on the best allocation and use of the main resources and funds of the organization. It is very important to actively use the production potential of the enterprise, it is necessary to observe the rhythm of production in order to load the production equipment to the maximum.

One of the important factors of increasing and improving the efficiency of enterprises is the economic regime. Conservation of resources must become a decisive resource to meet the growing need for fuel, energy, raw materials and supplies. Increasing production efficiency depends on the best use of fixed assets. It significantly increases production from the production potential, the maximum increase in production and, on this basis, the limit of production and, on this basis, the production from each block of categories. The result of the organization of intensive use of production facilities is the acceleration of the growth rate of additional products and capital investments. An important place in increasing

production efficiency is occupied by organizational and economic factors. Especially with the growth of social production with complications of economic relations of social production, their role is increasing.

In conclusion, it can be said that it requires further development of social infrastructure, which significantly affects the level of production efficiency. This is the improvement of forms and methods of management of the entire economic mechanism, improvement of planning, improvement of economic incentives. In the same group of factors, economic calculation and financial responsibility and other sensitive economic incentives and several factors of other farms are widely used. A special place in the activation of the economy of the enterprise belongs to the improvement of the quality of the product. This task should be constantly monitored and controlled, and should be the main factor in evaluating the performance of each work team.

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